

In vivo Megahertz Dynamic Optical Coherence Tomography of Human Skin

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Abstract: We demonstrate Megahertz optical coherence tomography (MHz-OCT) for *in vivo* skin imaging with dynamic contrast at different resolutions. This study presents recent advances and discusses challenges for clinical translation and real-time *in vivo* applications.

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1. Introduction

MHz-OCT has emerged as a powerful modality for high-resolution imaging of superficial tissue morphologies. Its high scan rates enable real-time, *in vivo* visualization of tissue architecture, offering promising prospects for clinical applications. However, conventional biopsy followed by histopathological analysis remains the gold standard for tissue characterization and malignancy assessment. Given the time-intensive nature of this approach, there is a pressing need for an immediate, non-invasive imaging technique capable of resolving biological tissue at a cellular level. Functional OCT imaging addresses this need by enabling the visualization of dynamic tissue processes *in vivo* without the requirement for exogenous contrast agents. In particular, dynamic optical coherence tomography (dOCT) provides histology-like cross-sectional images by detecting temporal signal fluctuations indicative of physiological and metabolic activity [1, 2]. This technique extends beyond conventional structural imaging by offering additional contrast mechanisms, enabling “optical biopsy”.

Despite its potential, the clinical implementation of dOCT has been constrained by long acquisition times and susceptibility to motion artifacts, limiting its practical applicability. A system operating at MHz A-scan rates with integrated real-time feedback could overcome these challenges, paving the way for advanced clinical applications. We have recently demonstrated the feasibility of MHz-OCT for dynamic contrast imaging in *ex vivo* porcine kidney tissue [3]. Building on its success in capturing dynamic cellular contrast in freshly excised tissue, we now investigate its applicability for *in vivo* imaging. Specifically, we evaluate different scanning optics and anatomical regions of the skin to optimize dynamic contrast visualization in living tissue. This study presents recent advances and challenges in MHz-dOCT for *in vivo* imaging at varying resolutions and discusses strategies to enhance its clinical utility.

2. Material and Methods

The OCT system used in this work is an all-fiber-based system equipped with a home-built FDML laser source and operated at an effective A-scan rate of 3.2 MHz [4]. For the demonstrated experiments, the center wavelength was set to 1310 nm, and with a spectral bandwidth of 110 nm, a theoretical axial resolution of 7 μm and an imaging range of 5 mm in air is achieved. The OCT interference fringes are detected by a 1.6 GHz balanced photodetector (PDB480C-AC, Thorlabs Inc., USA), and its signal is acquired at 4 GS/s (ATS9373, AlazarTech, Canada). The custom-built scanning unit consists of a pair of galvanometric scanners (dynAXIS 421, Scanlab GmbH, Germany) and a fiber-collimator (F260APC-C, Thorlabs Inc., USA). For different-resolution imaging, the experiments were conducted using three optical setups. High-resolution imaging was performed using two different scan objectives (M Plan Apo NIR 10X, M Plan Apo NIR 20X, Mitutoyo, Japan) in combination with a 4f optical relay system to fill the objective’s back aperture [3]. For standard-resolution imaging, a simple 50 mm spherical scan lens is used. The lateral resolution of the different optical setups was characterized using a high-resolution test chart (USAF-1951 negative target #55-622, Edmund Optics, USA). Detailed specifications of the optical scan lenses are listed in Table 1.

To assess the system’s performance for *in vivo* imaging, experiments were conducted on a volunteer’s hand. To minimize bulk motion artifacts and enhance optical penetration depth, the skin was pressed against a tilted cover glass with an interposed gel layer for refractive index matching. The optical focus was set at approximately 100 μm tissue depth. All *in vivo* experiments on human hands were conducted voluntarily by experts from our research group and were approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Lübeck.

For each optical setup, 250 repeated OCT line scans were acquired at a B-scan rate of 612 Hz and a dimension of 2048 \times 600 pixels. The dOCT algorithm was then applied to the processed OCT B-scans, which were exported in absolute values rather than the conventional logarithmic scale. This process involved Fourier transformation of the

OCT signal for each pixel along the time dimension. The amplitude integrals were separated into three frequency bands and color-coded to generate an RGB image, where blue represents slow motion frequencies (< 2.4 Hz / DC), green indicates medium motion frequencies (2.4–40 Hz), and red corresponds to fast motion frequencies (40–300 Hz). To enhance color contrast, adaptive histogram equalization was applied. Additionally, standard OCT intensity images were exported. To compare dynamic effects between both modalities, 250-times averaged B-scans are displayed.

Table 1. Specifications of the different scan lenses.

Parameter	20x	10x	Standard
NA	0.40	0.26	0.03
z_R	3.72 μm	7.25 μm	1.06 mm
P_{spl}	32 mW	22 mW	39 mW
Re_{Slat}	2.76 μm	3.48 μm	22.0 μm
FOV	1.0 mm	1.4 mm	13 mm

Abbreviations: NA, numerical aperture of the scan lens; z_R , calculated Rayleigh length; P_{spl} , power on sample; Re_{Slat} , lateral resolution; FOV, field of view (lateral).

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the acquired MHz-OCT images of a human fingertip, with dOCT images shown alongside standard intensity images to emphasize the additional contrast. Across all resolutions, characteristic skin features such as individual skin layers and the distinctive surface structure of fingerprint ridges are clearly visible. The outermost layer, the stratum corneum, appears as a dark, low-scattering layer approximately 200 μm thick, containing visible sweat ducts. Beneath this, the more scattering and therefore brighter epidermis extends downward into the underlying dermis.

Figure 1. Effect of dynamic contrast on *in vivo* MHz-OCT imaging at different resolutions.

The images show a human fingertip imaged with a 20x objective, 10x objective and standard 50 mm scan lens. Dynamic contrast OCT images (top row) are compared to the corresponding standard OCT intensity images, where 250 B-scans were averaged (bottom row). Arrows highlight individual vessels and the dashed line indicates the location of the vascular plexus. Color channels: blue (< 2.4 Hz / DC), green (2.4-40 Hz), red (40-300 Hz).

In the dOCT images, skin layers are more distinguishable than in standard intensity images due to their distinct color-coded contrast. The stratum corneum and epidermis, primarily composed of relatively static keratinocytes, appear blue, whereas the metabolically active dermis exhibits a green color, indicating medium dynamic activity. Notably, the epidermal-dermal junction is clearly delineated in the dOCT images, whereas it is barely visible in

intensity images. In particular, the dOCT image acquired with the 10x objective reveals the characteristic undulating pattern of this junction, formed by rete ridges extending downward from the epidermis and dermal papillae protruding upward, with remarkable clarity. Additionally, fine vascular structures, appearing red, are discernible in the dynamic contrast OCT images but are not distinguishable in intensity-based imaging. The high-resolution images allow visualization of individual blood vessels. In contrast, the standard-resolution image provides a rather larger lateral field of view (FOV), enabling the identification of the vascular plexus within the dermis. The high-resolution images, obtained using 20x and 10x objectives, reveal finer lateral detail and exhibit reduced speckle noise. However, due to the high numerical aperture (NA) and low incident power, the imaging depth is limited to approximately 800 μm . In contrast, standard-resolution images demonstrate greater optical penetration, reaching depths up to ~ 1 mm.

Compared to our previous *ex vivo* results [3], cellular structures are not resolvable in these *in vivo* images. This limitation probably arises from the use of two-dimensional line scans and the relatively low axial resolution of approximately 15 μm , which diminishes the benefits of high lateral resolution for cellular imaging. Additionally, the presence of a thick stratum corneum may further degrade effective resolution within the relevant tissue layers. To resolve cellular structures *in vivo*, true volumetric imaging with three-dimensional data acquisition is required, along with optimized optical parameters, to enhance contrast within deeper tissue layers.

A primary challenge in dOCT imaging is the presence of bulk motion artifacts. In the presented images, the finger remained at rest and was firmly pressed against the cover glass. Additionally, acquiring only 250 B-scans within 400 ms minimized motion artifacts between consecutive frames. However, the analysis of three-dimensional volumetric data requires longer acquisition times, increasing the likelihood of motion artifacts. Therefore, the implementation of precise three-dimensional motion correction algorithms will be essential before applying the dOCT-algorithm.

4. Conclusion and Outlook

The presented *in vivo* dynamic MHz-OCT images demonstrate label-free enhanced functional contrast. In particular, the improved differentiation of tissue layers holds significant potential for future automated segmentation approaches. However, achieving cellular resolution *in vivo* requires further investigation using three-dimensional OCT datasets. To avoid resolution degradation from scattering superficial tissue layers, future studies will also focus on different anatomical sites than fingers.

A key challenge for high-resolution *in vivo* imaging is the non-uniform displacement within soft tissue, which complicates numerical motion correction. Additionally, for clinical translation, real-time visualization and rapid acquisition remain essential but technically demanding. Addressing these challenges is crucial for advancing MHz-dOCT toward practical clinical applications. We will present new developments in volumetric dynamic MHz-OCT imaging and discuss strategies to enhance real-time *in vivo* imaging.

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